

Aza Triterpenes. Part-IV* : Synthesis of Ring A Fused (3,2-c)Isoxazoles and (3,2-c)Furazans of Methyl Oleanate and Methyl Betulinate†

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Ring A fused isoxazoles (III and IX) and furazans (VI and XII) of methyl oleanate and methyl betulinate were synthesised through their 3-keto-2-formyl derivatives (II and VIII) and through their 2,3-bis oximes (V and XI), respectively.

FUSION of heterocyclic rings to ring A of steroids have modified their biological activity¹ and in a few instances compounds with completely new type of biological activity have been produced². Even though the pentacyclic triterpenes and steroids are derived from a common biogenetic precursor and are structurally related, pentacyclic triterpenes have little biological significance. Attempts have been made here to induce biological activity by the fusion of isoxazole and furazan rings to ring A of methyl oleanate and methyl betulinate.

In the present investigation methyl oleanonate (I) and methyl betulononate (VII) were converted into their 2-formyl(2-hydroxymethylene) derivatives (II and VIII) by the action of ethyl formate and dimethyl formamide mixture in presence of sodium methoxide in dry benzene. The uv spectra of the formyl derivatives (II and VIII) exhibited a maxima around 285 nm which underwent a bathochromic shift of 20 nm in base, which proves that the formyl group is in equilibrium with its enolic form. The nmr spectra of the formyl derivatives have signals around δ 8.6 (1H, -CHO). The ir spectra of II and VIII [(a broad peak around 3150 cm^{-1} (chelated -OH) and 1680 cm^{-1} (>C=O)] also confirm their structures.

Methyl 2-hydroxy methylene olean 12-en-3-one-28-oate (II) and methyl 2-hydroxy methylene lup-20(29)-en-3-one-28-oate (VIII) furnished methyl olean-12-en-28-oate(3,2-c)isoxazole (III) and methyl lup-20(29)-en-28-oate(3,2-c)isoxazole (IX) when condensed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Manson and coworkers³ reported the formation of (2,3-d)-isoxazoles as the major product in the condensation of 2-formyl-3-oxo-steroids with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Meyer *et al*⁴ on the contrary reported the formation of (3,2-c)isoxazole as the major product in the condensation of 1-formyl-3,3-dimethyl cyclohexan-2-one with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Treatment of isoxazoles (III and IX) with sodium methoxide did not furnish α -cyano ketones eliminating the (2,3-d) structures (IIIa and IXa) for the isoxazoles. Hence the isoxazoles formed have the (3,2-c) structures which is in agreement with the latter's observation. NMR spectra of the isoxazoles have signals around δ 8.01 [1H(s)-isoxazole proton].

The methyl olean-12-en-28-oate (3,2-c)furazan (VI) and methyl lup-20(29)-en-28-oate (3,2-c)furazan (XII) were prepared by cyclisation of the corresponding 2,3-bis-hydroxy imino compounds (V and XI) with base. The 2,3-bis-hydroxy imino compounds (V and XI) were prepared by condensation

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of the respective 3-ones (I and VII) with isoamyl nitrite, followed by the treatment of the 2-hydroxy imino 3-ones (IV and X) formed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Methyl oleanonate and methyl betulononate used in this investigation were obtained by methylation followed by oxidation of oleanolic acid and betulonic acid, isolated in our laboratory from the roots of *Lantana camara* Linn⁵ and the stem bark of *Diospyros perigrina*⁶.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. UV absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were determined on a Perkin Elmer Infracord Model 237 and nmr spectra for solutions in deuteriochloroform with a Bruker spectrospin 80 MHz ¹H spectrometer with tetramethylsilane as internal reference. All the compounds showed consistent elemental analysis.

Synthesis of 2-formyl(2-hydroxy methylene) derivatives of methyl oleanonate (II) and methyl betulononate (VIII) :

A typical experiment is described.

To the pentacyclic triterpene 3-one (2 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) freshly distilled dimethylformamide (5 ml), freshly distilled ethylformate (5 ml) and sodium methoxide solution (25 ml) prepared from sodium (5 g) were added and refluxed for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, acidified and extracted with ether. The ether extract furnished the 2-formyl derivative as colourless solid (1.5 g) crystallising from methanol as colourless needles. [II, m.p. 180-82°; nmr: δ 8.6 (s, 1H of -CHO); ν_{nujol} : 3150 cm^{-1} (chelated -OH) and 1680 cm^{-1} (-CHO); uv $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$: 284 nm, underwent a bathochromic shift of 20 nm in base]. [VIII, m.p. 135°; nmr: δ 8.65 (s, 1H of -CHO); ν_{nujol} : 3145 cm^{-1} (chelated -OH) and 1680 cm^{-1} (-CHO); uv $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$: 285 nm, underwent a bathochromic shift of 20 nm in base].

Synthesis of (3,2-c) isoxazole of methyl oleanonate (III) and methyl betulonate (IX) :

A typical experiment is described.

A solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) in water (2 ml) was added dropwise during 10 min to a solution of 2-formyl(2-hydroxymethylene) derivative (1.0 g) in acetic acid (50 ml) at 60°. After 1 hr at room temp. the mixture was poured into water and the precipitate was extracted with ether. The ether extract furnished the (3,2-c)isoxazole derivative as colourless solid (0.8 g) crystallising from methanol as colourless needles. [III, m.p. 217-20°; nmr: δ 8.01 (s, 1H, isoxazole proton)]. [IX, m.p. 225°; nmr: δ 8.1 (s, 1H, isoxazole proton)].

Treatment of the crude isoxazoles (III and IX) with sodium methoxide :

Powdered sodium methoxide [prepared from sodium (0.5 g)] was added to the crude isoxazole (1 g) in tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) and stirred for 4 hr at room temp. It was then poured into water (50 ml), acidified and extracted with ether. The ether extract furnished a pale yellow solid (0.8 g). It crystallised from methanol as colourless needles. The reaction products from III and IX are identical with III and IX respectively. [mmp; co-tlc and superimposable ir].

Synthesis of 2-hydroxyimino derivatives of methyl oleanonate (IV) and methyl betulononate (X) :

A typical experiment is described.

A mixture of conc. hydrochloric acid (2 ml) and methanol (1 ml) was added to a solution of the pentacyclic triterpene 3-one (4 g) in benzene (35 ml) and methanol (2 ml). Isoamyl nitrite (1.5 ml) in benzene (2.5 ml) was then added dropwise with stirring during 15 min. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 1 hr, diluted with water (40 ml) and extracted with ether. The dried ether extract on removal of the solvent gave the 2-hydroxyimino derivative as a pale yellow semi solid (3.5 g).

Synthesis of 2,3-bis-hydroxyimino derivatives of methyl oleanonate (V) and methyl betulonate (XI) :

A typical experiment is described.

To the solution of 2-hydroxyimino derivative of the pentacyclic triterpene 3-one (3 g) in pyridine

(25 ml) and methanol (60 ml) hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.5 g) was added and refluxed for 15 hr. The cooled reaction mixture on dilution with water furnished the 2,3-bis-hydroxyimino derivative as a pink solid (2.5 g). It crystallised from methanol as light pink needles. [V, m.p. 145-50°; ν_{nujol} : 3500 cm^{-1} (OH); 3250 cm^{-1} (associated OH)]. [XI, m.p. 115°; ν_{nujol} : 3520 cm^{-1} (OH); 3250 cm^{-1} (associated OH)].

Synthesis of (3,2-c)furazans of methyl oleanate (VI) and methyl betulinate (XII):

A typical experiment is described.

A suspension of 2,3-bis-hydroxyimino derivative of the pentacyclic triterpene (1 g) in potassium hydroxide solution in ethyleneglycol (0.5 g in 2 ml) was heated at 180-190° for 0.5 hr during which time the reactants dissolved. The cooled solution was poured into water (10 ml) and the precipitated (3,2-c)furazan (0.5 g) was collected, dried and crystallised from ethanol as pale brown microprisms. [VI, m.p. 115°; ν_{nujol} : 2980, 2850, 1480, 1390, 1350, 1330, 1000, 910, 880 cm^{-1}]. [XII, m.p. 125°; ν_{nujol} : 3010, 2850, 1470, 1380, 1360, 1340, 1010, 920, 890 cm^{-1}].

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